

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

5 Tropical Indo-Pacific Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

Fred Short
University of New Hampshire
603-659-3313 cell
fredtshort@gmail.com
www.SeagrassNet.org

With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Th *Thalassia hemprichii*

Bioregion
5

Key

- Rounded serrated leaf tip
- Leaves 10-40 cm, often sickle-shaped
- Rhizome with scale leaves between shoots
- Dioecious
- Sometimes dark tannin spots on leaves
- Sometimes with red leaves in shallows

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

fruit

male

Si *Syringodium isoetifolium*

Bioregion
5

- Key
- Leaves cylindrical
 - Leaf tips taper
 - Leaves 7-30 cm long
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

fruit

Hp *Halodule pinifolia*

- Key
- Rounded leaf tips with marginal points
 - One central leaf vein
 - Pale rhizome with clean black leaf scars
 - Leaves 10 – 30 cm long
 - Depth intertidal to 20 m
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Hu *Halodule uninervis*

Bioregion
5

Key

- Leaves flat
- Leaf tip with 3 points
- Rhizome whitish with black leaf scars
- Leaves 10 – 30 cm long
- Depth intertidal to 20 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tip usually 2 points
- Leaves 2-22 cm long
- Rhizome whitish
- Dioecious
- Depth -1 to 20 m
- Sometimes leaves red or black

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Cr *Cymodocea rotundata*

- Key**
- Smooth rounded-to-squared leaf tip
 - Leaf scar fully encircles vertical stem
 - Narrow leaf blades (2-5 mm)
 - Leaves 7-20 cm long with 9-15 veins
 - Dioecious
 - Often with red leaves

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

female

fruit

Cs *Cymodocea serrulata*

- Key
- Serrated rounded leaf tip
 - Leaf scar not encircling vertical stem
 - Wide leaf blades (4-12 mm)
 - Leaves 6-15 cm with 13-17 veins
 - Triangle shaped sheath
 - Dioecious
 - Often with red cross-stripes on leaves

Flowering Parts

male

female

Seed

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Tc *Thalassodendron ciliatum*

Bioregion
5

- Key
- Cluster of leaves on an erect stem
 - Leaves 10-20 cm
 - Sickle-shaped leaves with serrated tips
 - Rhizome woody
 - Dioecious
 - Leaves often have red cross-stripes

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Ea *Enhalus acoroides*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Smooth rounded leaf tip
- Leaves 30 cm - 2m long
- Leaf edge rolls around tough fiber
- Wide leaf blades (10-20 mm)
- Rhizome with long black bristles
- Depth intertidal to 2 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

seedling

seed release

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Key

- Paddle-shaped leaves
- Leaf hairs on both sides
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth 0-30 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male & female

fruit

Ho *Halophila ovalis*

Bioregion
5

Key

- Oval-shaped leaves
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Depth 0-10 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

female

male

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hm *Halophila minor*

- Key
- Small oval leaves
 - 4 - 8 cross veins
 - Leaves 8 to 13 mm long
 - No hairs on leaf surface
 - Often intertidal
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering
Parts

Ho *Halophila hawaiiiana*

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Key

- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Dioecious
- Depth 0 -10 m

Flowering Parts

Hn *Halophila spinulosa*

Key

- Many oval-shaped leaves on a single stem
- Leaf edges finely serrated
- Wiry rhizome with stems to 30 cm
- Depth 0 -10 m
- Male and female different stems same plant

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

female

male

Hb *Halophila beccarii*

Bioregion
5

- Key
- 5+ elongated oval leaves in clusters
 - Leaves 0.5 –2 mm wide
 - Leaves up to 13 mm long
 - Often intertidal
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Flowering Parts

female

male

seed

Ht

Halophila tricostata

Bioregion
5

Halophila tricostata

Key

- Clusters of 3 leaves on vertical stem
- Leaf with mid-vein and no cross veins
- Leaf margins finely serrated
- Dioecious
- Depth 0-30 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hs *Halophila stipulacea*

Bioregion
5

- Elongated paddle-shaped leaves to 6cm
- Leaf stippled and bullate, tip serrated
- Distinctive scales cover the stem
- Depth 0-60m
- Dioecious
- Range expanding

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

G Koplovitz

female

Zj *Nanozostera japonica*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Smooth rounded leaf tip
- Narrow leaf blades (2-5 mm)
- Leaves 7-20 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth intertidal - shallow subtidal

Flowering Parts

Zc *Nanozostera muelleri*

Shaun Lee 2024

Tony Strazzari

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Round leaf tip deeply notched
- Strap-like leaf blades (1-3 mm wide)
- Leaves 10-60 cm long
- Persistent leaf sheath
- Monoecious
- Previously known as *Zostera capricorni*

Flowering Parts

Rachel Hooks 2024

de Kock et al. 2016

female

Zp *Nanozostera capensis*

Key

- Round indented leaf tip
- Leaf with staggered cross veins
- Strap-like leaf blades (0.5-2.5 mm)
- Leaves 10-115 cm long
- Persistent leaf sheath
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Global Seagrass Species References

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